

MVL Gates Algebra Over \mathbb{Z}_4

Abstract:

This paper presents a custom quaternary logic gate algebra defined over the cyclic group \mathbb{Z}_4 with state space $S = \{-1, 0, 1, 2\}$. A total of eight gates are defined across three categories: unary, binary, and ternary. The four arithmetic gates are derived from modular addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. The system is compared against binary and standard quaternary logic in terms of gate count and total bit representation.

Multi Valued Logic (MVL)

The system consists of a MVL gate configuration restricted to a four-state set under the algebraic properties of the cyclic group \mathbb{Z}_4 .

The state space of the system is restricted to finite set

$$s = \{-1, 0, 1, 2\}$$

All results wrap back into S using ϕ .

The Defined formula $\phi(x) = ((x + 1) \bmod 4) - 1$

Each gate operates on 2-bit encoded values, fully utilizing the 4-state capacity of a 2-bit signal.

The logic gate consists of Unary gates, Binary gates, and Ternary gates.

Unary Gates

P gate (Positive)

Shift the state position to the left ($-1 \rightarrow 0$)

$$P(x) = \phi(x+1)$$

N gate (Negative)

Shift the state position to the right ($0 \rightarrow -1$)

$$N(x) = \phi(x-1)$$

Binary gates

Sum gate (Addition)

$$a+b \bmod 4$$

$$f(a,b) = \phi(a+b)$$

Min gate (Subtraction)

$$a-b \bmod 4$$

$$f(a,b) = \phi(a-b)$$

Exp gate (Multiplication)

$$a \times b \bmod 4$$

$$f(a,b) = \phi(a \times b)$$

D gate (Division)

$$a \div b \bmod 4$$

$$f(a,b) = \phi(a \div b)$$

Ternary gates

MM gate (Minimum-Maximum)

Sort input From smallest to biggest then output the two end.

$MM(a,b,c) = [\min(\text{sort}(a,b,c)), \max(\text{sort}(a,b,c))]$

H gate (Half/Median)

Sort inputs, output the middle value.

$H(a,b,c) = \text{median}(a,b,c)$

The gates input and output would be demonstrated through truth table.

Truth table of P gate and N gate

Input/output	P gate	Input/Output	N gate
-1	0	-1	2
0	1	0	-1
1	2	1	0
2	-1	2	1

Truth table of Sum gate

A/B	-1	0	1	2
-1	2	-1	0	1
0	-1	0	1	2
1	0	1	2	-1
2	1	2	-1	0

Truth table of Min Gate

A/B	-1	0	1	2
-1	0	-1	2	1
0	1	0	-1	2
1	2	1	0	-1
2	-1	2	1	0

Truth table of Exp gate

A/B	-1	0	1	2
-1	1	0	-1	2
0	0	0	0	0
1	-1	0	1	2
2	2	0	2	0

Truth table of D gate

A/B	-1	0	1	2
-1	1	0	-1	0,-1
0	0	0	0	0
1	-1	0	1	0,1
2	2	0	2	1

Due to variable output, MM gate and H gate is demonstrated via examples.

MM gate

$$MM(-1,1,1)=[-1,1]$$

$$MM(1,2,0)=[0,2]$$

$$MM(2,1,-1)=[-1,2]$$

$$MM(-1,-1,0)=[-1,0]$$

H gate

$$H(-1,1,0)=1$$

$$H(2,-1,2)=2$$

$$H(1,0,2)=0$$

$$H(0,1,1)=1$$

The arithmetic gates SUM, MIN, EXP, and D form a complete set of fundamental operations over \mathbb{Z}_4 .

The unary gates P and N provide directional shift, and the ternary gates MM and H provide sorting-based selection.

Comparison With Binary and Standard Quaternary

Property	Binary	Quaternary (standard/universal)	This system
State space	{0,1}	{0,1,2,3}	{-1,0,1,2}
Gate count	7	6	8
Popularity	Extreme	Low	None
Input bits	13 bits	16 bits	32 bits
Output bits	7 bits	14 bits	20 bits
Total bits	20 bits	30 bits	52 bits

Based on the table above, this system has a total bit count 2.6 times greater than binary and 1.73 times greater than standard quaternary.

Standard quaternary logic maintains structural similarity to binary, which is the primary reason it remains binary-derived.

Binary logic serves as the foundation for standard quaternary and most existing systems. This system does not derive from binary as a base. Division, which is typically avoided or omitted in standard logic systems due to its complexity, is defined here as a primitive gate. Through modular arithmetic and dual output for ambiguous results, division is handled without contradiction or error. Rather than dismissing division, this system is built around it.

Conclusion

This paper defines a custom quaternary logic gate system over \mathbb{Z}_4 using the state space $S = \{-1,0,1,2\}$. The four arithmetic gates are derived from mod 4 addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division, with the remaining gates providing positional shift and sorting operations.